

THE INFLUENCE OF ABIOTIC FACTORS ON THE PHENOLOGY OF THE *CACOEZIA CRATAEGANA* HB.

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a study on the bioecological development features of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in the Ile-Alatau and Dzungar Alatau State National Parks. The main objective of the research was to identify the key factors influencing pest development, determine its phenological and environmental characteristics, and identify the most vulnerable stage of the hawthorn leafworm in order to implement timely and effective pest control measures. Particular attention was given to the role of abiotic factors, especially air temperature and humidity, which significantly affect the timing of developmental stages and the overall phenology of *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. The study established the precise periods of occurrence of different developmental stages and determined the relationship between climatic conditions and insect activity. The results showed that temperature conditions largely regulate the rate of larval development and the onset of pupation and adult emergence, while air humidity influences survival and activity of larvae. Based on field observations conducted during the 2018–2019 seasons in the foothill zone of the Almaty region within the Ile-Alatau and Dzungar Alatau State National Parks, it was determined that the pest develops in one generation per year under these environmental conditions. Depending on weather factors, the duration of the most hazardous period of the pest ranged from 35 to 40 days. The obtained data made it possible to summarize the seasonal dynamics of hawthorn leafworm activity and compile a phenological calendar of its development. Accurate knowledge of phenological patterns and environmental parameters, particularly temperature and humidity, is essential for improving monitoring systems and ensuring timely and effective pest management strategies.

Key words: *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb., the Sievers apple, the Zhetysu Alatau, the Iley Alatau, Kazakhstan, pests, insects.

Introduction

The Sievers apple tree is a relict species known since the Oligocene times, representing a Central Asian mountain type. The particular value of the species is that it is the custodian of the unique germplasm and the ancestor of many cultivars of apple trees [1, 2]. Natural plantations of the Sievers apple tree have no analogues in the world plant community [3]. They are currently recognized as having global world significance, as the world's only natural genetic basis for the maintenance and development of the apple culture [4, 5].

Relevance of the study lies in the fact that over the past few decades, the range of this species has significantly decreased, due to state and economic changes, genetic and environmental pollution of wild populations, as well as emergence of dangerous pests around the area.

The area of the Sievers apple tree in Kazakhstan covers the mountainous regions of the east, southeast and south of Kazakhstan, stretching from Tarbagatai to the Western Tien Shan. The main tracts of wild apple forests are found in Tarbagatai (an area of about 300 hectares), the Zhetysu Alatau (3800 ha), the Iley Alatau (1300 hectares) and in the Western Tien Shan [6]. In the Western Tien Shan, the apple tree is found mainly in small groves scattered in the gorges, occupying only one large massif of 50 hectares area, that is the grove "Kara-alma" in the Aksu river canyon located in the Aksu-Zhabagly reserve. Among the species of the genus *Malus* Mill., the Central Asian wild-growing Sievers apple tree has a great intraspecific diversity [7], a wide range of variability in biological characteristics,

resistance to winter cold, drought and heat, and immunity to pests and diseases.

A.D. Dzhangaliev, researcher of wild apples in the Zhetysu and Iley Alatau in the mid-XX century, studied the Sievers apple tree within the Kazakhstan mountain system at the phytocenotic, species and population levels. His studies showed that local forests have high polymorphism and genetic duplication [8, 9].

According to experts, the situation is already alarming as the unique intraspecific diversity of Kazakhstani populations of wild apple is now rapidly decreasing, which reduces the value of its gene pool. It is already difficult to restore these resources in a natural way, since in many local populations there is practically no natural regeneration of the apple tree. In addition, the proximity of cultivated apple orchards directly adjacent to wild populations of fruit forests represent a serious challenge. The buffer zone along natural populations is often not observed. In addition, threats to wild fruit forests stem from alien plant species, insect pests and diseases of the wild apple and of other wild species of fruit plants [10].

Early seasonal defoliation of trees is especially difficult for the fruit tree organism, resulting in significant reduction of the radial growth of trees lasting several years upon the outbreak of number of the insect pests [11]. Such reduction in growth of the tree contributes to infecting it with pathogenic fungi, bacteria and insect pests, which in turn can cause further drying out of trees.

One of the main conditions for the plant anti-pest protection is the timeliness of various complex

measures based on use of phenological data [12]. Signalling and predicting the timing of pest emergence and development is a major and sophisticated task, needed by modern techniques for insect pest control. It is important to note that the family of leafworms (Tortricidae) from the order Lepidoptera occupies a special place among other insect pests [13, 14].

It is worth noting the need to study the phenology of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb., since this representative of the family of leaf rollers causes significant harm to fruit and berry plants.

In the nature, there is a huge number of various harmful insects that destroy fruits and leaves of fruit and berry plants. Mountain apple forests of Kazakhstan are permanent centers of reproduction and areal of the hawthorn leafworm. Here is its brief description. Main coloration of fore wings is brownish-gray, in males with yellow pollen. The pattern is dark brown (distinct in males, with a clearly visible light border, blurred in females), it consists of an oblique root spot with a rounded apex, an obliquely positioned broad and inflated median band, tapering very sharply at the front of the wing (often the band does not reach the leading edge) and merged anteroposterior and outermost bands as a gradually tapering saber-like curved band. Hind wings are unicolor brownish-grey, in females with reddish patches at apex. Eggs pale yellow, slightly flattened cylinders with rounded apex, 0.7-0.8 cm high and 0.5 mm thick; in clutch they are arranged 20-90 eggs

vertically to substrate in arched, single rows in oval, flat grayish-brown shields 0.2-0.5 cm in size. Overwintering, the shields turn white and resemble splashes of lime. Larva is 20-23 mm in length, dark gray or greenish black; head, thoracic legs, prothoracic and anal scutes and shields at the base of body spines are black, shiny. Abdominal legs (sclerotized externally) with triple crown of 52-72 claws, anal legs with 47-59 claws in triple medial horseshoe; pupa 13-16 mm, dark brown, slightly shining; cremaster as elongate, not flattened longitudinally wrinkled papillae, armed with eight hooked setae, of which four are located on its conical apex and two on each side.

Material and research methods

The study was carried out using methods of laboratory analyses, route and stationary surveys of the Sievers apple tree plantations located in the territory of the Iley-Alatau and Dzungar Alatau state national parks.

In Zhetysu Alatau, the optimal zone for growing Sievers apples corresponds to the altitude of 1,200-1,500 m above sea level on the northern slopes and 1,200-1,600 m on the southern slopes. In the Iley Alatau, the apple tree grows at an altitude of 900-1,500 m a.s.l. and 1,500-1,700 m a.s.l. on the southern slopes. Optimal conditions for growing wild apples in the Iley Alatau were observed on northern slopes at 1,300-1,600 m a.s.l. (figure 1).

Fig. 1. – Schematic map of the location of monitoring sites

The research subjects were leaves infected by pests at different stages of development: larva of different ages, pupa, and adults.

The 2023-2024 studies were carried out in laboratory and in the fields.

To determine the species identity of pests, the following were used: identifiers of agricultural pests, pests and beneficial insects; methodological recommendations and guidelines [15].

During field observations and collecting, the butterflies and larva were placed in glass jars of 0.5l or glass test tubes; the leaves of the Sievers apple tree were also placed with larva, that ones where larva were residing. Separate test tubes also contained the leaves of the Sievers apple tree infected with larva. These boxes were noted with serial numbers, information about the place and time of collection, the plant, the nature of its damage and other data were registered in a log. Later, when molting and for keeping, the caterpillars were placed into separate test tubes.

In laboratory, tubes with rolled leaves were covered with gauze and labelled. The larva was kept and fed in test tubes, under gentle conditions of warmth, light and moisture, needed for normal development of the larvae. Especially, the containers with larva were kept under direct sun rays short time in order to avoid harmful sweating of the containers, their waterlogging and overheating.

To identify the species, samples of biological samples were inspected with binocular microscope and were photographed.

Research results and discussion

The prerequisite for successful protection against hawthorn leafworm is the onset of the vulnerable stages

of development, which is the optimum time for treatment.

In order to determine the treatment timing, it is important to know the exact dates of the following stages in the pest's development:

- the beginning of the mass flight of the moths;
- the start of mass egg laying;
- the beginning of mass hatching of larvae.

The larva emerge at the end of April - beginning of May, when the average temperature reaches 10°C. The larvae penetrate the buds, eat them up and then move on to blossoms and flowers [15]. The larvae of older plants fold the leaf along the central vein and bind it inside out, later on they bind together a few leaves so that they form a silkworm-containing pocket. The feeding period of the caterpillars lasts 35-40 days, or in 25 days under favourable temperature conditions. The larvae hatch in feeding places among the leaves. The puping takes 10-16 days at an average temperature of 16 to 19°C. Flight of butterflies is quite long, lasting from the end of May until the third decade of July. The females lay their eggs in the tree barks and branch forks. Development stage data on hawthorn leafworm, obtained in the laboratory conditions, are shown in Figure 2 and Table 1.

Fig. 2. – Various stages of the development of the hawthorn leafworm, obtained in the laboratory conditions (1 – an egg, 2 – larvae in leaf, 3 – larvae, 4, 5 – pupae, 6 – imago) (Photos: Gulzhanat Tanabekova)

Table 1.

Phenogram for the development of the hawthorn leafworm 2018-2019

April			May			June			July			August		
I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
0	0	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω	□	+□	+0	+0	+0	+0	+0	0
		▲	▲	▲										

- – pupae;
- + – imago;
- 0 – eggs laying;
- Ω – hatching of larvae;
- ▲ – especially dangerous period.

Table 1 indicates a particularly dangerous period for the fodder plant - the stage of the mothers of 1-3 growth, which appear from the third decade of April to the first decade of June. According to our observations,

the mass flight of butterflies is often observed after precipitation. Table 2 provides data on phenological observations of the hawthorn leafworm in the Iley and Zhetysu Alatau in 2018-2019.

Table 2.

Phenology of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in 2018-2019

Development stages	Data		Night temperatures, T°C		Relative humidity, %	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
Beginning of hatching of the 1 st larvae from overwintered eggs	27.04.	26.04.	10	11	76	73
Mass emergence of the 1 st larvae and the start of active feeding	08.05.	11.05.	17	23	34	33
2 nd larvae	12.05.	16.05.	18	17	53	49
3 rd larvae	18.05.	21.05.	17	23	42	48
4 th larvae	22.05.	26.05.	19	21	44	38
5 th larvae	29.05.	03.06.	18	20	40	57
Beginning of pupation	01.06.	07.06.	19	22	51	45
Mass pupation	08.06.	12.06.	19	18	52	51
Beginning of the imago flight	11.06.	15.06.	20	20	60	57
Mass imago flight	27.06.	02.07.	25	26	39	37
Beginning of the egg laying	02.07.	09.07.	24	28	33	39
The mass egg laying	19.07.	27.07.	28	29	28	22
Beginning of diapause	03.08.	16.08.	23	24	44	40

The duration of various stages of development of the hawthorn leafworm in the Iley and Zhetysu Alatau according to observations in 2018-2019: full life cycle - 1 year (one generation), egg (embryo with wintering) - 280-300 days, caterpillars - 35-40 days, pupa - 10-16

days, imago - 30-60 days. Influence of temperature indicators and relative air humidity on the phenology of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in 2018-2019, it is presented below in the form of a graph (Fig. 3-5).

Figure 3 – Influence of temperature (°C) on the phenology of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in 2018-2019

Figure 4 – Influence of the relative air humidity (%) on the development of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in 2018

Figure 5 – Influence of the relative air humidity (%) on the development of the hawthorn leafworm *Cacoecia crataegana* Hb. in 2019

Conclusion

This type of pest affects all types of apple trees, and in some cases it can develop on pear tree. Affected trees become vulnerable to unfavorable environmental factors, which reduce the overall resistance, causing depletion of trees and decrease of fruit production in subsequent years. For effective control of the hawthorn leafworm, it is important to know its biological characteristics [17].

The research conducted in the period from 2018 to 2019 allowed to reveal that with termination of the winter stage the 1st generation larva start to come out at 10°C under conditions of middle mountains. Approximately 35-40 days later, they pass to the puping stage at an average daytime temperature of 18-28 °C. This stage of development lasts about 10-16 days. The mass puping takes place in the first decade of June at an average daytime temperature of 19-29 °C. The first imago appear in the second decade of June at a temperature of

20 °C. Mass flight of butterflies is observed every week at an average daytime temperature of 25-32 °C. Their life lasts from the beginning of June to the end of July. It was found out that the mass egg-laying occurs at the end of June. The hawthorn leafworm winters in eggs.

Remarkable is the resistance of the Sievers apple tree against diseases and pests, even though the Sievers apple tree in the Iley Alatau is damaged by 25%, in the Zhetysu Alatau by 18%, meaning that the Iley Alatau has suffered more damage by the hawthorn leafworm than the Zhetysu Alatau.

In order to combat the pest, accurate knowledge of phenological and ecological data is crucial to know. Establishment of modern phenological data is to be followed by mechanical, biological or chemical control measures.

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